

EFFECTIVENESS OF LANGUAGE COACHING IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Anarkulova Diana

dianakoskarbaeva@gmail.com

Scientific advisor: Shukurova Zumratkhon

zumradxons@gmail.com

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Abstract. The effectiveness of language coaching in learning a foreign language includes the individual's learning style, motivation, and the quality of the coaching itself. This research focused on the ways to help EAP students achieve their goals in learning foreign languages through some strategies and techniques. It defined the notion of language coaching, considered its distinctive features from traditional teaching methods, and described the fundamental strategies and techniques that have been applied to the practice of teaching English.

Keywords: *language coaching, setting goals, cultural awareness, GROW model, interactive communication.*

Аннотация. Эффективность языкового коучинга при изучении иностранного языка зависит от индивидуального стиля обучения, уровня мотивации и качества проводимого коучинга. Данное исследование направлено на выявление способов помощи студентам ЕАР в достижении своих языковых целей через применение определенных стратегий и методов. В работе определено понятие языкового коучинга, обсуждаются его отличия от традиционных методов обучения, а также описываются фундаментальные стратегии и методы, используемые в практике преподавания английского языка.

Ключевые слова: *языковой коучинг, постановка целей, культурная осведомленность, модель GROW, интерактивное общение.*

Annotatsiya. Chet tilini o‘rganish til o‘rgatishning samaradorligi individual o‘rganish uslubiga, motivatsiya darajasiga va ko‘rsatilayotgan murabbiylik sifatiga bog‘liq bo‘ladi. Ushbu tadqiqot EAP talabalariga maxsus strategiya va usullardan foydalanish orqali til maqsadlariga erishishda yordam berish yo‘llarini aniqlashga qaratilgan. Maqolada til bo‘yicha murabbiylik (kouching) tushunchasi ta‘riflanadi, uning an‘anaviy o‘qitish usullaridan farqlari muhokama qilinadi, shuningdek, ingliz tilini o‘qitish amaliyotida qo‘llaniladigan fundamental strategiya va usullar tavsiflanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *til o‘qitish, maqsadni belgilash, madaniy xabardorlik, GROW modeli, interaktiv muloqot.*

Learning foreign languages has become more comfortable with the availability of different resources, whereas it can still be challenging. Each individual has their style and method for learning languages, while one method may work for one person but not another

([Mark Ollerton](#)). Language coaching through interactive communication with a coach (consultant, coach) can help to grow and improve language skills more effectively [Djampulatova N.M., 2022; Gabriella Kovács, Hungary, 2019]. In recent years, a new direction has been actively developing – language coaching and teachers calling themselves coaches have also appeared. Coaching (training, consulting) is a way of development in which a specialist, called a coach, supports and trains a student or client to achieve a specific personal or professional goal, while language coaching is a way to achieve a goal in learning a foreign language with the support of a mentor coach.

Language coaching is a personalized approach to language learning that focuses on the learner's individual needs, goals, and preferences. It is a dynamic and collaborative process that involves working with a coach who provides guidance, feedback, and support to help the learners achieve their language learning objectives. The coach helps the learners identify their **strengths** and **weaknesses**, set realistic goals, develop strategies for improvement, and overcome any obstacles they may encounter along the way. In the process of coaching, there is a search for an internal resource to achieve the task, and then a personality-oriented method is used, which involves the use of open questions (what? how? why?). The teacher-coach does not tell the student what to do, but by asking questions, allows the student to come to the need to complete training tasks himself. In addition, such an individual approach is aimed at identifying the existing working strategies of the student to achieve the goal.

Unlike traditional teaching methods, in which the teacher has a pre-made lesson plan and is forced to "cut off" everything superfluous so that the lesson corresponds to the plan, thereby limiting the student's creative abilities to a strict lesson plan, the structure of the language coaching session is quite flexible. The student's existing experience conditions it. With this approach, the student's abilities are also considered. Sometimes even tasks that cause unpleasant emotions in the student are avoided and replaced by others that are more pleasant for the student. Thus, only the ultimate goal remains strictly fixed, and the ways to achieve it may vary significantly.

Techniques and Strategies of Language Coaching

When teaching by the method of language coaching, it is advisable to give the student as much information as possible about the methods that the teacher uses. It contributes to the formation of partnerships on the part of the student. Language coaching techniques and strategies are what a specialist uses to achieve the intended goal and improve their language skills by providing personalized support and guidance, for example, **SMART** technology and cultural awareness. SMART technology is a new way to set working goals. The smart goal-setting system helps learners organize their thoughts when setting a goal. It lets them choose a reasonable deadline and ensures they have what they need to achieve the goal. It also helps them give very specific tasks to everyone involved. "SMART" stands for Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound. Each letter of the SMART abbreviation means a criterion for the goals' effectiveness.

In the "Cultural Awareness" section, a coach helps learners develop an understanding of the cultural context in which the language is spoken. Coaches can provide information on cultural norms, customs, and practices that can impact language use and help learners develop cross-cultural communication skills.

It is important to note that most of the techniques and strategies of teaching in language coaching are determined by the specific purpose of the student (student, client). The fact is that the feeling of disappointment from learning a foreign language is usually associated with an incorrectly set goal. The most common goal of "learning a foreign language" is very abstract and vague, and therefore it is difficult to measure and notice progress, as a result of which the student quickly loses motivation. The absence of an assessment criterion and an incorrectly set goal can lead to the fact that the student will work a lot on grammar and perform written exercises, and when he tries to speak in a foreign language, he will not be able to say anything, since he has not trained this competence. It can lead to frustration and, as a result, loss of interest in learning the language. Therefore, at the initial stage, the trainer-teacher, with the help of open questions, finds out the student's goal and fixes it in writing.

Methodology

There was a practice in using the language coaching method in real life. The practice was with 5 EAP (English for Academic Purposes) students who already knew English well, which helped to facilitate the process. The first day was introductory, and communication began with open questions: *Why did you choose this language (English), and how do you feel when you use this language?* These questions were key to further research, so we learned their feelings, reasons, and weaknesses. Our practice aimed to achieve the goal of specific improvements in language skills and motivation support. The hypothesis of the practice: feel comfortable in using language, achieve a goal, and evaluate a weakness.

In the process of language coaching, the teacher used some strategies and techniques such as communication, motivation, personalization, the wheel of language balance, and the GROW model.

The "GROW" model is a method of achieving goals. It first appeared in the UK in 1980. Since then, it has been actively developed and used in coaching.

GROW is an abbreviation of the four stages of the technique:

G- Goals (what do you want? aspirations, desires)

R- Reality (where are you now? current obstacles, current situation)

O- Options (what could you do? strengths, resources)

W- Will (what will you do? personal actions – what, when, where will be done to achieve the goal)

As a result of GROW model, we discovered weaknesses in our students, such as a language barrier and less motivation. Communication and personalization helped fix them. We started giving examples of overcoming language barriers and feeling calm, providing personalized feedback and support based on the learner's specific needs and

interests, and encouraging learners to use the language they are learning as much as possible. For less motivation, we motivated learners to stay engaged and committed to the learning process. Coaches used various techniques such as goal setting, positive reinforcement, and encouragement to keep learners motivated.

The wheel of language balance technique is a great way to see and analyze the current state visually. The basic idea is that each of us has six essential language skills, each of which strongly impacts the quality of our learning. Here students need to evaluate their skills from 0 to 10 points:

Vocabulary	4. Reading
Grammar	5. Listening
3. Speaking	6. Writing

Most of the students had good points in all skills, but vocabulary and listening were the least. In this way, we can find out exactly what skills our student is weak in and improve these skills with the help of models, assignments and practice.

With these techniques and strategies, we were able to learn about our students and achieve our goals. The result showed that three students were 75% able to achieve their goals overcome the language barrier, and feel more confident in using language, and two students were 60% able to get the motivation to study the language further.

In this article, we have listed only the main list of coaching techniques that a coach can combine when conducting sessions with a client. There are many of them, and their usage depends primarily on how effectively the session with the client is proceeding. Based on our research, language coaching helps achieve a specific goal but also, based on the life experience in learning and using the language, gives examples and tasks to achieve the goal and support a learner.

In conclusion, language coaching as a method of individual training by a coach (consultant, coach) in the form of interactive communication is a sufficiently productive way of teaching a foreign language, especially at the initial stage of learning foreign languages. The use of this method in mini-groups of studying foreign languages also seems promising.

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